

GENERATION Z'S EXPOSURE TO, INTEREST IN, AND USAGE OF SOCIAL MEDIA AND PRINT MEDIA

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ABSTRACT

With the continued rise of the internet and social media, the use of print media, which is often considered a more reliable source of information, is declining. The purpose of this study was to determine the level of exposure, interest, and use of social media and print media among Generation Z students, particularly Grade 11 students of Holy Name University, academic year 2022–2023. Participants included students from ABM, HUMSS, and STEM strands, who were selected using stratified random sampling. Using a quantitative descriptive-comparative design, exposure was examined based on time of use, sites visited, and types of reading materials used. The relationship between strand and media exposure was also examined using the chi-square test, while ANOVA was used to determine differences in interest and use. The data showed that participants had higher levels of exposure to social media, particularly Facebook and TikTok, where they spent up to five hours per day. Meanwhile, they had lower levels of exposure to print media such as books and other reading materials. The study also found that exposure, interest, and use of social media and print media were not significantly different based on strand. This indicates that students from different academic strands have similar attitudes towards the two forms of media.

Keywords: *Social Media, Print Media, Generation Z*

INTRODUCTION

In real-time, Generation Z, more popularly known as Gen Z, witnessed the rise of social networking sites, which have become extremely popular internationally. The Global Web Index (2019) reported that the Generation Z demographic spends an average of 8 hours per day on the Internet, with around 2 hours and 55 minutes dedicated to social media. The same index showed that Generation Z social media usage—marked by a preference for bite-sized, short visual content on Instagram, YouTube, and TikTok—has exceeded the time spent on social media by Millennials (born 1981–1996). In recent years, the use of social media has increased globally.

Junco et al as cited in Owusu-Acheaw & Larson (2015) acknowledges the growing extent of social media use among youth today. This assembly of websites, services, and Internet-based activities allow people to work together, build communities, take part, and share. Guy (2012) mentions that Bryer & Zavataro had identified that these technologies include blogs, wikis, media (audio, photo, video, text) sharing tools, networking platforms (including Facebook), and virtual worlds now used to to facilitate communication, promote collaboration, and facilitate discussion between involved parties.

However, one alarming phenomenon in the field of literature is the steep decline in reading habits among those who belong to Generation Z (born 1997–2012), as shown in a report by YouGov and Scholastic Inc. (2019). The proportion of young people who read every day has decreased from "60 percent in the late 1970s to 12 percent," according to the findings of a study by Twenge et al. (2019) on the rise of digital media. Having grown up with the pervasive influence of gadgets, the internet, and social media, Generation Z's ease with ubiquitous technologies has earned them the moniker "digital natives".

Reading habits are well-planned, intentional routines that are created through reading of "one's own accord," as stated in Owusu-Acheaw's (2016) definition of reading habits. Cultivating a healthy reading habit is paramount to educational success, as pointed out by Palani (2012).

The rise in social media usage, never before seen in modern history, has influenced the decrease in Generation Z's reading habits. After all, reading long-form text such as books, articles, and journals does require patience, intention, and a lengthy attention span. Researchers from around the globe have published studies that correlate social media usage and reading habits.

The goal is to determine the levels of exposure, interest, and usage of both social media and print media by Generation Z learners in light of the present decline in reading habits. Particular focus is given to Grade 11 students, whose varied strands of specialization in senior high school (i.e., STEM, ABM, and HUMSS) may factor into specific habits when it comes to social media and print media.

This study is anchored on two theories, namely Ball-Rokeach & DeFleur Media System Dependency Theory (1976) and Chen et al.'s Interest-Driven Creator (IDC) Theory

(2018).: Ball-Rokeach & DeFleur (1976) created the Media System Dependency Theory to explain how a certain type of media can have a more significant effect on a person's life. The theory claims that the more a person relies on media to satisfy their needs, the more critical the media's role in their life. According to the proponents, the influence of the media is said to be strongly dependent on the interaction between the more extensive social structure, the role that the media plays in that system, and how the public reacts to the media and vice versa, according to the proponents of this theory. The Interest-Driven Creator (IDC) Hypothesis was created by Chan et al. (2018) as a means of reviving Asian students' waning enthusiasm for learning due to the rigors of examination-driven education. The philosophy is founded on three concepts: interest, invention, and routine. Using the habit loop, students repeat learning tasks (such as reading lengthy texts) as part of their everyday routine. By establishing such behaviors as habits of their own will, kids establish "creative habits" (p. 2).

Reading habits are any activity that demonstrates a preference for types of reading or reading preferences (Sangkao, 1999). Shen as mentioned in Munsod-Fernandez (2021) explains that individuals organize their reading according to their preferences. Reading can be broken down into three categories: frequency, quantity, and content. Students spend less time reading books because technology and media have gotten better. Instead, they spend more time watching TV, talking online, and using social media.

A recent poll from Gallup.com (Jones, 2022) has found that college students, primarily a Generation Z population, displayed a steep decline in their reading habits in the past year. The popularity of reading as a hobby is on the wane, especially with the availability of social media and other Internet options to spend one's time. The majority of the average Generation Z's waking hours is devoted to the fast consumption of photos, viral memes, and short-form videos on apps, in lieu of other ways of spending time (Luttrell & McGrath, 2021). These "lost" activities include reading long-form content, as can be readily found in books, articles, and journals.

Kojo et al. (2018) looked at how tertiary students in Ghana read in the age of social media. They did this to show that the implications of social media usage on reading habits are not mere speculation. The results showed that constant access to social media platforms has negatively affected how students read. So, the researchers came to the conclusion that students' use of social media has a "statistically significant effect on their academic performance and, to some degree, their reading culture (p. 1)."

Kojo et al. (2018) found that even though [students] enjoy social media, some of them admit they spend more time each day online accessing social media platforms. As a result, it has distracted students in the classroom and even while they are reading in the library. Due to the decrease in reading time, this has impacted their reading culture. (p.7-8)

Muthyalai-Chetty and Kishore (2017) echoed the same sentiments in their study, stating that social media has resulted in distractions in reading habits due to a decrease in reading time. Social media usage has effectively decreased the amount of time

students have left to read their books and other study materials (Ofuani and Gberedio, 2009).

As a habit, however, reading requires the person to devote their full attention to the text. One must read with patience: enough to process lengthy paragraphs, and to comprehend the text's deeper meaning. Such a skill has been in steady decline since the Internet first became mainstream, followed by the popularity of social media websites like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. Today, the most popular means of leisure is not reading a book, it is scrolling through one's social media (Avunduk, 2021).

To show the influence of social media even more, Rafiq et al. (2019) investigated how social media affects reading habits. Social media fosters socialization, which helps students with their studies, and students find it easy to search for and use information on social media. The drawback is that social media causes students to become distracted while studying. Additionally, the study found that excessive use of social media can lead to a decrease in academic performance and affect students' ability to concentrate during lectures. Therefore, it is important for students to limit their social media use and prioritize their academic responsibilities.

Research Questions

The study aims to determine the levels of exposure, interest, and usage of both social media and print media by Generation Z learners, particularly the Grade 11 students at Holy Name University for the academic year 2022-2023. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How many hours per day do students spend on social media and print media?
2. How often do students:
 - 2.1 Visit different social media sites?
 - 2.2 Use print media materials (e.g., newspapers, magazines, pocket novels, etc.)?
3. What is the students' level of interest of using social media and reading print media?
4. How often do students use social media and print media for the following purposes?
 - 4.1 academic purposes
 - 4.2 information
 - 4.3 For socialization (social media only)
 - 4.4 For leisure reading (print media only)
5. Is there a significant relationship between the academic strand of Grade 11 participants and their exposure to social media and print media?

METHODOLOGY

The study was quantitative in nature and specifically employed descriptive comparative study and used the crosstab analysis model, chosen for its ease in comparative analysis of data from the various Grade 11 strands: Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics, Accountancy, Business, and Management, and Humanities, and Social Sciences (STEM vs. ABM vs. HUMSS) offered in a private senior high school in Bohol. The sample size was determined via the stratified random method, with a proportionate ratio to reflect the actual distribution of Grade 11 students per strand. As such, one strand may cover a larger sample size when compared to the others. The data gathering was conducted with the use of an electronic questionnaire.

This private school was chosen as the specific environment because it meets the following criteria: (1) being an excellent repository of print media, (2) having the virtual infrastructure needed to use social media in-campus, and (3) the majority of its senior high school population owning smartphones. The university is home to a number of libraries and learning centers distributed across the campus. These sources of printed materials such as books, newspapers, and magazines could be found in the Integrated Basic Education Department and in the various colleges: all of which were easily accessible to Generation Z learners.

Stratified random sampling was used in the selection of the participants. The process as to how the researchers identified the specific participant from each strand are: First, the researchers gathered all the lists of the grade 11 students and numbered them from number one up until the last student. Second, the researchers divided the total population by the total number of students in each strand and multiplied it by the desired sample size.

This study ensures that, given that the participants are under the legal age of 18, all necessary precautions are taken, including obtaining parental consent and the participants' assent. Additionally, since the study involves only a survey, there are no concerns regarding learning losses during the process.

The researchers used a validated survey questionnaire delivered as an electronic questionnaire via Google Forms. The final Google Form was presented to the participants with the title, "Generation Z's Exposure, Interest, and Usage of Social Media and Print Media."

RESULTS

Table 1
Participants' Exposure to Social Media and Print Media (In Hours)

Number of hours	Social Media		Print Media	
	F	%	F	(%)
Less than 1 hour	10	4.8	143	68.1
1 hour	10	4.8	34	16.2
2 hours	26	12.4	21	10.4
3-5 hours	29	13.8	8	3.8
More than 5 hours	135	64.2	4	1.9
Total	210	100.0	210	100.0

Table 1 presents the participant's level of exposure to both social media and print media. The table reveals that most of the participants spend time on social media for more than 5 hours with a frequency of 135 or 64.2% while 29 students or 13.8% among the specified participants spend at least 5 hours. This means that the participants spent longer screen time on social media sites. The data is overwhelming, but it cannot be denied because as can be seen, Generation Z social media users spend longer time due to the variety of features that social media sites have to offer such as posting pictures, watching entertaining contents, liking, and commenting different posts, and interacting activities that can hold them long in using social media platforms.

On the other hand, with print media, most participants spend less than 1 hour reading printed media with a frequency of 143 or 68.1 %, while only 4 (1.9%) participants spend more than 5 hours reading printed media. This means to say that participants are reading printed media significantly less. Based on the given data, it is alarming that only a few in their generation devote themselves to reading print media, specifically books.

Table 2
Participants' Frequency of Visit to Different Social Media Sites

Social Media Sites	Mean	Description
Facebook	4.29	Always
Tiktok	4.15	Often
Youtube	3.80	Often
Instagram	3.50	Often
Snapchat	1.71	Never
Reddit	1.57	Never
9Gag	1.28	Never

The mean response of 4.29 reveals that the participants always use Facebook. Its platform caters to a wide variety of users and combines multiple kinds of media, such as images, text, and messaging. Facebook permits "free data," allowing users to browse even without a data subscription and provides "free access" to all users. As a result of this modification, participants can now access Facebook more frequently than before, indicating that Facebook is more accessible than other social networking sites.

Table 3
Participants' Frequency of Use of Different Printed Materials

Print Media Materials	Mean	Description
Newspaper	1.89	Rarely
Magazines	2.06	Sometimes
Pocket Novels	2.08	Sometimes
Dictionary	2.43	Sometimes
Brochure	2.08	Rarely
Leaflets	1.86	Rarely
Encyclopedia	2.12	Rarely
Books	3.22	Sometimes
Textbooks	3.16	Sometimes
Catalogs	1.94	Rarely

The data reveals that participants sometimes used printed books with a mean response of 3.22 and textbooks with a mean response of 3.16 respectively. Books and textbooks are the most widely used printed materials, as these are readily available in libraries and at home. Although books and textbooks have the highest mean, it can be gleaned that the participants only sometimes use the said printed materials. It can be further understood that the participants use books and textbooks due to their availability and accessibility over the other aforementioned printed materials.

Table 4
Participants' Level of Interest in Using Social Media and Print Media

Social Media			Print Media		
Item	Mean	Description	Item	Mean	Description
Comfortable when spending hours on	3.92	Agree	Comfortable when spending hours	3.90	Agree

social media			reading print media.		
Anxious when using social media	2.94	Neutral	Anxious when I read print media.	2.54	Disagree
Interested in reading the content on social media	3.87	Neutral	Interested in reading print media to get information.	3.54	Agree
Spend more time on social media that I forgot my assignment	2.74	Neutral	Spend more time reading print media that I forgot my assignment.	2.35	Disagree
Learn about social media that would help my academics	4.06	Agree	Read print media that would help my academic	3.69	Agree
Social media does not help me in my studies	2.33	Disagree	Reading print media does not help me in my studies.	2.13	Disagree
Grand Mean	3.31	Neutral	Grand Mean	3.025	Neutral

Table 4 shows the participants' level of interest in terms of using social media and print media. The grand mean indicates a neutral level of interest for both social media and print media. Specifically for social media, the participants are not able to ascertain their interest such as in being comfortable when spending hours on social media, feeling anxious when using social media, being interested in reading the content of social media, and in spending time on social media that results in forgetting their assignment.

Table 5

Participants' Usage of Social Media and Print Media for Academic Purpose

Item	Social Media		Print Media	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. to solve my academic problem.	3.67	Often	3.60	Often
2. to do research work.	4.10	Often	3.62	Often
3. to prepare for examinations	4.31	Always	3.90	Often
4. to join academic group discussion	4.16	Often	3.61	Often
5. to collaborative learning.	4.18	Often	3.68	Often
Grand Mean	4.08	Often	3.68	Often

The grand mean of usage of social media is 4.08 and usage of print media is 3.68 which are both qualitatively expressed as often. This means that for academic purposes the

participants often use social media and print media in preparation for their exams, solve academic problems, do research, academic group discussions, and collaborative learning. Independently, a mean response of 4.31 is observed in the item that pertains to use of social media in preparation for examination which is qualitatively described as always.

Table 6.

Participants' Usage on Social Media and Print Media for Information Purposes

Item	Social Media		Print Media	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
1. to have access to different news	3.78	Often	3.57	Often
2. to share new ideas	3.73	Often	3.50	Often
3. to get job-related information	3.30	Sometimes	3.15	Often
4. to get information regarding current social events	3.99	Often	3.48	Often
5. to do research work	4.07	Always	3.63	Often
Grand Mean	3.77	Often	3.47	Often

As regards participants' level of usage of social media and print media to acquire information, social media has a grand mean of 3.77, and print has a grand mean of 3.47 which are both qualitatively expressed as often thus, participants either use social media or print media to get information. However, there are isolated data that reveal a different picture of the overall impression of the data. It says that when it comes to getting job-related information, social media is less reliable to them. This can be construed as not all local job opportunities are posted in the social media. However, when it comes to doing research, they turned to it for help.

Table 7

Participants' Usage of Social Media for Socialization Purposes

Items	Mean	Description
1. To become more sociable	3.74	Often
2. To create my social identity	3.29	Sometimes
3. To strengthen interpersonal relationships	3.55	Often
4. To keep in touch with my relatives	4.13	Always

Grand mean	3.68	Often
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Table 7 shows the data on the participants' usage of social media in terms of socialization. It reveals grand mean of 3.68 which is described as often. This means that participants use social media often so that they will become more sociable, to create their social identity, stretch intrapersonal relationships and most importantly to keep in touch with their family.

As the data shows, participants often use social media that allows them to keep in touch with their relatives, with a mean response of 4.13.

Table 8
Participants' Usage on Print Media for Pleasure Purposes

Item	Mean	Description
I read print media...		
For leisure	3.24	Sometimes
For entertaining stories	2.7	Rarely
For a way of (free) entertainment	3.33	Sometimes
I prefer reading print media than attending social gatherings	2.00	Rarely
To alleviate depression	3.12	Sometimes
Grand Mean	2.88	Sometimes

Legend: 4.21- 5.00, Always; 3.41- 4.20, Often; 2.61- 3.40, Sometimes; 1.81- 2.60, Rarely, 1.00-1.80 Never

Table 8 outlines the data on participants' usage of print media for pleasure purposes. Usage on print media for pleasure purposes has a grand mean of 2.88 which was qualitatively expressed as sometimes. The data implies that participants only used or read for some time in print media to find leisure, to read entertaining stories, to find entertainment and to alleviate their depression. It reveals that the participants' usage purpose for print media is for entertainment purposes, with a mean response of 3.33.

Table 9
Relationship between Grade 11 Participants Strand and Exposure to Social Media and Print Media

Variables Correlated	Chi-square value	p-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Strand vs. Social Media Exposure	5.584	0.232	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Strand vs. Print Media Exposure	2.937	0.568	Accept Ho	Not Significant

significance at 0.05 alpha level

From the crosstabulation of strands and social media and print media exposure, Table 9 presents the relationship between participants' strands and exposure to social media as well as to print media. It reveals that the researchers failed to reject the null hypothesis since the probability values 0.232 and 0.568 of each correlation are both greater than the level of significance set at 0.05 alpha. The result implies that participants' exposure to both print media and social media is not dependent on their strands. Further, the "no significant value" implies that the findings of high exposure to social media across strands and low exposure to print media across strands are not conclusive to the whole population of Grade 11 students.

DISCUSSION

As can be seen, Generation Z spend less time reading printed books for two main reasons. Firstly, due to over time, advances in information technology and the media have caused students to spend less time reading books and more time watching television, conversing online, and immersing themselves in social media activities. Secondly, due to the emerging evolution of reading materials from printed to digitalized reading materials like books, journals, blogs, and other written content that can be accessed and read using electronic devices such as smartphones, tablets, or e-readers. These materials can be "born-digital," which means they were created in a digital format, or they can be converted into digital files. Portable and accessible, digital reading materials have several advantages over traditional print materials as digitized reading materials are light in weight, accessible, convenient, and provide clear text.

A similar conclusion was reached by Rideout, Foehr, and Robert's study which found that Generation Z youngsters are more exposed to media than any other activity other than sleeping, with participants spending an additional 67 minutes per day consuming and engaging with media. This quantity is currently reaching close to 8 hours of overall daily exposure to electronic multimedia when multitasking is taken into consideration (Turner, 2015.)

Also, the 2019 Global Digital Report from the website DataReportal shows that most social media users around the world are younger than 24 years old. Many of these users, based on their age range, were junior and senior high school students. According to the same survey, the Philippines has the highest user population as a percentage of the total population, 46 percent of the population, or 107 million people, are considered to be active users, and they spend an average of 10 hours and 2 minutes every day on social media (Mindajao, 2021).

There are factors that researchers look into consideration as to why the data of the participants' frequency in using printed materials, specifically books, and textbooks, are noticeably less. First, the less utilization of books and textbooks in gathering significant information related to academics. Generation Zs has become more adaptive to using internet-based information due to the fact that it is accessible and less time-consuming. Second, is the teacher's method in disseminating instructional materials, most especially

in the university where the study was conducted the blended method is being adopted. Teachers use links for the students to have access, portable document format (PDF), and concept notes excerpted from the book so that students may no longer need to look for textbooks and books.

Furthermore, research has shown that Generation Z's frequent exposure to social media sites on a daily basis has made an impact on their interest and usage of print media materials and has effectively decreased the number of times students have to read their books and other study materials.

Boyd and Ellison (2007) state that students who spend a lot of time on social media sites read less, which can harm their grades and performance. In 2014, Ictech reported that many students who have access to social media use it to chat and look up non-educational information. Now that social media offers instant gratification, students seem less inclined to read for enjoyment.

On the other hand, the neutral level of interest of the participants for both social media and print media is a perplexing reality. The researchers comprehend that participants are merely hesitant to show that they invest time in social media.

On the one hand, the neutral interest of the participants in printed media can be attributed to the participants' purpose of their engagement in print media. For these participants, they read print media because they have a specific purpose like getting information and for academic reasons but their anxiousness to read which has a mean of 2.54 is described qualitatively as disagree. This means that they only read when they are obliged to do but they are not into reading that much.

The outcome is indeed anticipated, as social media fulfills its function in helping students to study for exams and engage in group learning. Knowing that social media platforms like Messenger and Instagram are messaging platforms, it allows students to communicate and exchange thoughts and ideas with their classmates. Aside from that, these platforms have features for video conferencing, which means that they can virtually be in a meeting doing collaborative learning. But looking at the data in more depth, it can be seen that there is not much difference between each indicator. This can only mean that they use social media for school, whether it is for tests, research, assignments, or other school-related tasks.

On the other hand, although the data clearly show that print media is being used less for academic purposes, the research did not identify specific reasons why this is no longer as expected. There is not enough data or literature in the current study to explain the factors behind the decline in interest in using printed materials. However, it can be assumed that using print media requires more time and patience in manually searching for information, and some materials may contain outdated data that is no longer relevant to the current needs of students. In future research, it is suggested that additional data be collected to explore the reasons why students are not returning to using print media.

The results are consistent with the findings of Rafiq et al. (2019), who stated that social media helps in learning by facilitating social interaction and quick retrieval of information. However, their study also highlighted the negative effects of excessive use of social media, such as impaired concentration and decreased academic performance. Despite this, the current data shows that the participants have a positive use of social media, especially when it is supported by print media for more orderly and thorough research.

Therefore, it can be concluded that although print media and social media are often used for academic purposes, social media is becoming an increasingly popular tool even for academic purposes.

This result can be interpreted that participants' purpose of usage of social media is for socialization, which allows them to be sociable, build strong connections, and strengthen their relationship with their relatives through the medium use of identified social media sites such as Facebook, TikTok, and YouTube, which allow their friends and family to interact and socialize by sharing pictures, posting videos, updating their status, liking, and commenting on each of their posts, which develops socialization and interaction through social media sites. In that case, they could still maintain their relationship and socialize with others. In addition, with more extensive networking and contacts with local, national, and worldwide peers, social media platforms have boosted students' social engagement. It has also given students a place to socialize with their classmates, the university, and society.

Moreover, aside from the abovementioned advantages of using social media for socialization purposes, socialization improves a student's reading and writing skills, as well as their knowledge, critical thinking, ability to solve problems, ability to communicate, and ability to make connections. It also helps a student integrate into society by allowing them to make a meaningful contribution. Students benefit more from the learning environment when they are allowed to read, write, participate, listen, and speak. Through socialization, students can participate well in social situations when they are allowed to contribute, share ideas, and engage in social discourse.

Abbas et al. (2019) noted that social media platforms have facilitated communication and interaction among students in the modern era, as well as sharing and exchanging ideas for continuous learning.

From the gathered data, despite the fact that participants sometimes read print media, it can still be seen that participants still place value in reading print media materials in terms of providing entertainment and leisure, despite the prevalence of social media and its increased active users globally.

In addition, participants are still pleased and being entertained by print media reading materials such as books and textbooks, as can be seen in the previous data in Table 4. This can be interpreted as meaning that participants still show an interest in print media materials for leisure and entertainment purposes, indicating that print media reading

materials are not yet completely replaced by digital alternatives and continue to have a significant role in providing pleasure and leisure activities for readers.

In the literature reviewed by Čepič et al., (2024), reading for pleasure is defined as the act of voluntarily engaging in reading for personal pleasure with eager expectation of the sense of accomplishment that will result from the act of reading. In most cases, it means utilizing materials that are reflective of our own decisions at a time and location that are convenient for us. The studies show that reading for pleasure not only improves literacy but also provides cognitive, emotional, and social benefits, including deeper self-understanding and participation in culture and society.

According to Allan et al. and The Reading Agency, participation in activities focused on reading for pleasure has a positive impact on the development of children's social skills. Meanwhile, Sanacore emphasized that when children frequently read for pleasure, they experience the importance of reading as both an efferent and aesthetic process. As a result, they develop a greater sense of purpose in reading, which helps to promote their reading habits (Clark & Rumbold, 2006).

As regards the crosstab results used to establish the significant relationship between the academic strand of Grade 11 participants and their exposure to social media and print media, it reveals that for the HUMSS strand, out of 28 participants, there are 20 (71.43%) who are oftentimes to always exposed to social media or spend 3-5 hours per day. While in the STEM strand, out of 151 STEM students, there are 117, (77 %) who are oftentimes to always exposed to social media or spend 3-5 hours per day. And in the ABM strand, out of 31 ABM participants, there are 27 (87%) ABM students who are also oftentimes to always exposed to social media or spend 3-5 hours per day.

Overall, out of 210 participants from varied strands, 164, (78.1%) are oftentimes to always exposed to social media or spend 3-5 hours per day. This finding suggests that the varied strands are oftentimes or exposed to social media for 3-5 hours per day, to always or exposed to social media for more than 5 hours per day. Hence, social media takes up a great chunk of their time per day. This implies that social media plays a significant role in the lives of senior high school students, regardless of their chosen academic strand. It is important for educators and parents to be aware of this and to incorporate responsible social media use into their guidance and teachings.

Meanwhile, regarding the strands and print media exposure in the HUMSS strand, out of 28 participants, there are 21 (75%) who are rarely to never or exposed to printed for less than 1 hour. While, in the STEM strand, out of 151 STEM participants, there are 128 (84.77%) who are rarely to never or exposed to print media for less than 1 hour. And for the ABM strand, out of 31 STEM students, there are 28 (90%) who are rarely to never or exposed to print media for less than 1 hour.

Overall, out of 210 participants from varied strands, there are 177 (84.23%) who are rarely to never or exposed to print media for less than an hour. This indicates that a significant number of students from the varied strands of the HUMSS, STEM and ABM strands have

limited exposure to print media, which may have implications on their reading culture, reading comprehension and academic performance. It is important for educators to address this issue and provide appropriate interventions to support these students.

Therefore, exposure to both social media and print media is not dependent on the students' strands. Regardless of their chosen strand, their probability of getting exposed to social media and print media will not vary.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that Generation Z participants from Grade 11 are more exposed to social media compared to print media materials, and they often visit popular platforms such as Facebook and TikTok. Although social media dominates their daily lives, they also use both social media and print media for learning and information purposes. The findings show that they use social media not only for communication and socialization, but also to search for academic information, while they still value print media as a source of pleasure and entertainment.

Recommendations

1. Integration of social media into class activity to ignite interaction and collaboration for meaningful and engaging learning experiences.
2. Teacher's integration of social media sites into their teaching practices to be more engaging.
3. Parents supervise Generation Zs when using social media, make printed materials available, and encourage reading.
4. Students limit screen time and make time to read print media.
5. Future researchers may conduct the same study to determine if these findings hold true for a larger and more diverse population.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

To facilitate fluency in the gathering of data, the researchers submitted a letter of approval to the Ethics Review Board (ERB). Before proceeding to the data gathering proper, the researchers handed an informed consent form to each participant to be discussed with their parents to get valid approval since the participants are still minors. When the parents approved, the researchers also sought the participants' assent. The researchers read to the participants the terms in the informed consent form and verified their understanding of the content of the said form. When all approvals had been received, the researchers proceeded immediately with the data gathering.

All participation would be voluntary. They were given the option to withdraw from the sample if they chose not to participate. In cases of withdrawal from the study, the researchers anticipated substituting the participant and looking for another based on the characteristics of the person who withdrew to participate as regards sex, gender, age, and grade level. However, no one withdrew from the study.

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